

**APPROACHES AND ACTIVITIES THAT HELP TO DEVELOP
INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION COMPETENCE.**

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Annotation: Being acquainted with the some activities and approaches which is basically include in some types of them can assist in the area of communication actively , in terms of business context or maybe while you are traveling another country which put people in a intricate situation in which individuals have to integrate with residents who live in that background and there some basic , vague approaches that can help to obtain some profound knowledge that are able to give some databases about that culture, this article can give some examples and ways to develop.

Keywords: ICC, cognitive dimension, knowledge, attitude, skill, awareness, active listening, cultural awareness, word choice, normal instructions, a culture of respect.

The first thing that readers and learners must know what actually ICC is and the long version of it is like that intercultural communication competence which refers the ability and experience to be able to communicate with the people who are living totally different countries which do not have any similar customs with another countries. It includes gestures, phrases, customs and topic customs word which are belong to solely to that particular country. There are numerous cognitive dimensions of ICC to assist to give exact definition, process to increase it , so they are :

1. Knowledge: culture-specific insights, values, practices, and global issues.
2. Attitude: openness, acceptance, and readiness to adapt to other cultures.
3. Skills: researching, understanding, and relating to varying cultures; language proficiency.
4. Awareness: introspective comparison of one's own native culture to that of others.

Besides, we mentioned before that there are approaches to heighten and help create the normal environment to work or reside in that are , they are :

1. Practice active listening.

All ancestors said that to comprehend the situation which are complicate to get the grips , listening should be the starting point of creating the tranquil settings or spot , as an example which is highly comparable and suitable for this statement to prove that is " If teacher asks a question about animal mainly reptiles from students so that to check them whether they are listening or not , since solely students who are attentive to class time are able respond this query because of being absorbed into current time in which teacher is speaking. By actively listening, to get the meaning will be really straightforwardly.

2. Be careful with word choice .

It is significantly essential to develop this skill , especially the communication between employees and employers as while employees are doing something important to envision the next action which means like using terms and specific phrases that belongs to the field which are called jargons.

For instance, the word " gyp" is used to describe the verb of " to cheat " in British English, but this word can be used to racial slur in Romania. That's why understanding the context of languages or the main meaning of languages is an important factor that should be obtained firstly rather than other features.

It is very useful to use interactive games during the lesson. This makes the lessons interesting and effective. In addition, during the lesson, inactive students are interested in their peers and try to participate in the lesson and interesting games. The use of different methods in the lessons ensures the effective passage of educational activities and requires professional skills from the teacher.

The use of different methods depending on the type of science is also used to determine the interests of students. Each student in the classroom is considered to have different abilities in different areas. Being able to bring them to the surface and realize it in time requires the professional skills of the teacher. For example, mathematics can be used effectively with various interesting mathematical games, memory games, logical games.

Different methods are used depending on the subject of the lesson. At first, it is recommended to use games that are easy and engaging for students. Because the attention and attention of all students is focused on the teacher and the lesson. The methods prepared on the topic will help the student to remember and re-enforce. And it should also be mentioned that conducting lessons taking into account the mental state of students is the main goal of the effectiveness of the lesson.

It is possible to use the methods of finding words from foreign languages, i.e. English or Russian, rocket game, and who wins. As an example, it can be mentioned that the rocket game is played in the following order. A picture of a rocket is drawn on the board and questions are pasted on it. Divided into two groups, students take turns answering the questions. The rocket of the group that fails to respond cannot fly. Because in order for the rocket to fly, it is necessary to lighten the load, that is, to answer the questions. The group that answers all the questions is considered the winner and will be evaluated at the maximum level. This + method requires agility, dexterity, and knowledge from each other. And it should also be mentioned that group games teach students to work as a team, how to manage it, and unity. Encouraging students who actively participated during the lesson will increase their interest in science and will be active in the next lessons.

In conclusion, it should be said that modern, interactive methods help students to increase their knowledge potential and master them in a solid way. An effective lesson is beneficial not only for the students, but also for the students. Each of the used methods is important in increasing the level of knowledge and revealing inner abilities. And it should be said that it is also reasonable to determine which aspects of a student have deficiencies.

If more attention is paid to the lesson not only from the theoretical part, but from the practical side, the lesson will become more interesting and it will be easier to achieve the goal set by the teacher. It is useful for students to use various modern methods and to be able to use them effectively in the lesson. The quick question and answer method also helps students to improve their speed and reinforce the topic. And the use of various colorful picture games allows you to concentrate and increase interest in the lesson. Because young children are interested and eager for colorful things.

References:

1. Adams R. B. Jr., Rule N. O., Franklin R. G. Jr., Wang E., Stevenson M. T., Yoshikawa S., Ambady N. (2009). Cross-cultural reading the mind in the eyes: An fMRI Investigation. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, 22, 97-108.
2. Adler N. J. (2008). *International dimensions of organizational behavior* (5th ed.). Mason, OH: Thomson South-Western.
3. Alhejji H., Garavan T., Carbery R., O'Brien F., McGuire D. (2016). Diversity training programme outcomes: A systematic review. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 27, 95-149.
4. Ames D. L., Fiske S. (2010). Cultural neuroscience. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, 13, 72-82.

5. Argyris C., Schön D. (1996). Organizational learning II: Theory, method, and practice. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
6. Barak M. E. (2014). Managing diversity: Toward a globally inclusive workplace (3rd ed.). New York, NY: Sage.
7. Bartlett F. C. (1932). Remembering. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
8. Ben-Ari A., Strier R. (2010). Rethinking cultural competence: What can we learn from Levinas? *British Journal of Social Work*, 40, 2155.
9. Bennett M. J. (2004). Becoming interculturally competent. In Wurzel J. S. (Ed.), *Toward multiculturalism: A reader in multicultural education*. Newton, MA. Retrieved from http://www.idrinstitute.org/allegati/IDRI_t_Pubblicazioni/1/FILE_Documento.pdf.
10. Bezrukova K., Jehn K. A., Spell C. S. (2012). Reviewing diversity training: Where we have been and where we should go. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 11, 207-227.

